

JAVASCRIPT HAQIDA TUSHUNCHA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda JavaScript haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: JavaScript, dinamik veb-saytlar, veb-brauzer, Brendan Eich.

JavaScript - bu interaktiv va dinamik veb-saytlarni yaratish uchun keng qo'llaniladigan dasturlash tili. U birinchi marta 1995 yilda Brendan Eich tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan va hozirda ECMAScript standartlari organi tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. JavaScript barcha asosiy veb-brauzerlar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan yuqori darajali, talqin qilingan dasturlash tilidir.

JavaScript asosan veb-brauzerda ishlaydigan mijoz tomoni skriptlarini yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, u serverda emas, balki foydalanuvchining kompyuterida bajariladi. Bu foydalanuvchi tajribasini tezroq va sezgirroq qilish imkonini beradi, chunki kod to'g'ridan-to'g'ri brauzerda serverga borishni talab qilmasdan ishlashi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, JavaScript-dan Node.js kabi texnologiyalar yordamida server tomonidagi skriptlarni yaratish uchun foydalanish mumkin.

JavaScript-ning eng mashhur qo'llanilishidan biri bu interaktiv veb-sahifalarni yaratishdir. Masalan, JavaScript-dan ochiladigan menyular, tasvir slayderlarini yaratish va shaklni tekshirish uchun foydalanish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, animatsiyalar, qalqib chiquvchi oynalar va modal oynalar kabi dinamik effektlarni yaratish uchun ham foydalanish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, JavaScript vazifalar ro'yxati va kalendarlar kabi veb-illovalarni yaratish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin.

JavaScript odatda HTML va CSS kabi boshqa veb-texnologiyalar bilan birgalikda ishlatiladi. HTML veb-sahifaning tuzilishini ta'minlaydi, CSS esa maket va dizaynni yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript veb-sahifaga interaktivlik va dinamik xatti-harakatlarni qo'shish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin.

JavaScript o'rganish uchun nisbatan oson til bo'lib, barcha asosiy veb-brauzerlar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Sintaksis C va Java kabi boshqa dasturlash tillariga o'xshaydi va JavaScript-ni o'rganish va boshlashga yordam beradigan ko'plab manbalar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, Angular, React va Vue.js kabi ko'plab ramkalar va kutubxonalar mavjud bo'lib, ular ishlab chiqish jarayonini soddalashtirish va murakkab ilovalarni yaratishni osonlashtirish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, JavaScript mijoz tomoni tilidir, shuning uchun u foydalanuvchi kompyuterida ishlaydi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, kod foydalanuvchiga ko'rinadi va ular xohlasa, uni ko'rishi va o'zgartirishi mumkin. Bu xavfsizlik bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin, shuning uchun har qanday foydalanuvchi kiritgan ma'lumotlarni serverga yuborishdan oldin tekshirish va tozalash muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, JavaScript kuchli dasturlash tili bo'lib, interaktiv va dinamik veb-sahifalar va veb-illovalarni yaratishda keng qo'llaniladi. Uni o'rganish oson va barcha asosiy veb-brauzerlar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi va boshlashingizga yordam beradigan ko'plab manbalar va ramkalar mavjud. Biroq, mijoz tomonidan skript yaratish bilan bog'liq xavfsizlik muammolarini yodda tutish kerak.

JavaScript bilan ishlashda quyidagi bir nechta narsalarni yodda tutish kerak:

- 1) JavaScript voqealarga asoslangan tildir, ya'ni kod tugmani bosish yoki sahifa yuklanishi kabi muayyan hodisalarga javoban ishlaydi. Bu yanada interaktiv va sezgir foydalanuvchi tajribasiga imkon beradi.
- 2) JavaScript erkin terilgan tildir, ya'ni siz o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilganingizda uning ma'lumotlar turini ko'rsatishingiz shart emas. Bu kodni yanada moslashuvchan qilishi mumkin, lekin disk raskadrovkani ham qiyinlashtirishi mumkin.
- 3) JavaScript - bu ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan til, ya'ni siz kodingizni tartibga solish va tuzilish uchun ob'ektlar va sinflarni yaratishingiz mumkin. Bu prototiplar va konstruktorlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi.
- 4) JavaScript-da turli xil o'rnatilgan funktsiyalar va ob'ektlarni ta'minlovchi boy standart kutubxona mavjud. Bunga massivlar, satrlar va sanalar, shuningdek, muntazam ifodalar va taymerlar kabi kengaytirilgan xususiyatlar kiradi.
- 5) JavaScript ko'pincha dinamik veb-ilovalarni yaratish uchun AJAX va JSON kabi boshqa texnologiyalar bilan birgalikda ishlatiladi. AJAX asinxron veb-sahifalarni yaratishga imkon beradi, ular sahifani yangilamasdan yangilanishi mumkin. JSON - bu server va mijoz o'rtasida ma'lumotlarni uzatish uchun tez-tez ishlatiladigan engil ma'lumot almashish formati.
- 6) JavaScript-dan React Native va Electron kabi texnologiyalar yordamida platformalararo ilovalar yaratish uchun ham foydalanish mumkin.
- 7) JavaScript jonli va faol hamjamiyatga ega, ya'ni o'rganish va boshlashga yordam beradigan ko'plab manbalar va ramkalar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, boshqa ishlab chiquvchilar bilan bog'lanishingiz va so'nggi tendentsiyalar va eng yaxshi amaliyotlardan xabardor bo'lishingiz mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab konferentsiyalar va uchrashuvlar mavjud.
- 8) JavaScript-da juda ko'p uchinchi tomon kutubxonalari va ramkalari mavjud bo'lib, ular ishlab chiqish jarayonini soddalashtirish va murakkab ilovalarni yaratishni osonlashtirish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin, masalan, JQuery, Lodash, axios, Moment.js va boshqalar.
- 9) Nihoyat, JavaScript doimiy ravishda rivojlanib bormoqda, yangi xususiyatlar va yangilanishlar muntazam ravishda chiqariladi. Til imkoniyatlaridan to'liq foydalanish uchun eng so'nggi yangiliklardan xabardor bo'lish muhim.

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